

TRAINER'S SKILL AS A MARKETABLE PRODUCT IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

The article is based on the assumption that trainers have special skills, efficient marketing of which may change the existing marginalized scenario altogether. In this context, it has defined the key terminologies like trainer, trainer's skills, market and marketing. It has further examined the existing market potential as well as its problems and prospects. In doing so, the article has narrated a number of theoretical approaches, made both supply and demand side analysis, explored the opportunities and challenges. In order to utilize the explored opportunities of marketing the trainer's skills by overcoming the challenges, the article has suggested a number of indicative strategies to be pursued by the trainers. These include unity of the trainer community, development of own professional standard, appropriate public relations and market studies to further explore scope and opportunities for devising ways to penetrate the market.

INTRODUCTION

While everyone emphasizes on the importance of training and development in nation building as well as in successful business management, training activities remain under-funded and trainers continue to be under-privileged. In the present era of globalisation and open market economy with increasing pressure for downsizing the government and reducing public expenditure, trainers as professionals find themselves marginalized. However, trainers have special skills, efficient marketing of which may change the scenario altogether. In this context, this paper aims to expand the boundaries of training and development profession by examining the market potentials as well as its problems and prospects. This paper limits its focus on management level training as opposed to vocational training. It focuses on both pre-service training and programmed in-service training as opposed to informal on the

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job training. This paper assumes that trainers have special skills; there is a potential market for their skills; trainers are willing to market their skills and there are potential buyers of these skills. With aims, scope and assumptions identified, this paper proceeds to delineate the analytical framework.

FRAMEWORK OF ANALYSIS

In order to remove ambiguity, key terminologies have been defined first. These terminologies include Trainer, Trainer's Skills, Market and Marketing.

Trainer

Trainer is a person who is engaged in training other people. Training means facilitating specific knowledge and skills in a structured way (NGFL: 2000). It can also be defined as learning opportunities (for example, courses and workshops) that focus on workplace learning and performance (MVU: 2002). Trainer is a person who directs the growth of learners by making them qualified or proficient in a skill or task, uses coaching, instructing, and facilitating techniques to accomplish the learning objectives (NEIU: 2002). Trainers belong to a very broad category of individuals comprising both vocational and management level ones. Vocational trainers are outside the scope of this paper. Management level trainers can be classified into four sub-categories: First, trainers who are involved in actual delivery of knowledge and skills, such as Presenters, Instructors, Facilitators, etc.; Second, trainers who are involved in management of training programs, such as Training Director, Training Manager, Training Coordinator, etc.; Third, trainers who are involved in planning, evaluation of training programs, such as Planning, Research and Evaluation Officers, Evaluation Consultants, etc.; Fourth, trainers who are predominantly entrepreneurs or innovators, such as Dr. Saadat Husain, President of the Bangladesh Society for Training and Development (BSTD), Mr. M. Mosharraf Hossain, Managing Director, Rapport Bangladesh Limited, Mr. Anish Barua, Managing Director, Communica, etc.. Training skills vary across different types of trainers. This is also possible that an individual may work in various capacities at the same time and may possess diverse types of training skills. This paper primarily focuses on training delivery skills and defines a trainer as an individual who actually facilitates learning of the participants. However, the role of training entrepreneurs is also frequently highlighted upon.

Trainer's Skills

This has already been noted that different types of trainers need different skills. Sing (2000) maintains that "In order to conduct a good training course, one should develop and build following training skills: a) communication skill, b) questioning skill, c) motivation skill, d) body gestures, and e) handling difficult situation." The Training Clinic (2004) identifies the following as essential skills of a trainer: a) how to ask questions and give directions; b) listen, observe and record; c) paraphrase, clarify and focus; d) give feedback; e) encourage participation and collaboration; and f) coach to correct mistakes. As trainer has been conceptualised as an individual who facilitates acquiring knowledge and skill, this paper focuses on training delivery skills only. Such skills include the following:

- Communication skills: written, verbal and non-verbal
- Relational skills
- Assessment skills
- Situation handling skills
- Leadership skills
- Program designing skills
- Instruction material preparation skills
- Expertise on the subject.

Market

Market can be defined in terms of a product and/or a geographical area, for example, US Apparel Market. Here, Apparel Market is a product market and US Market is a geographically identified Market expressed jointly as US Apparel Market. The idea of Market can be conceptualised as "A place, or mechanism, where buyers and sellers can communicate and complete an exchange for goods or services if they agree on the price and terms and conditions of sale." (CBA, UC: 2004). It can also be conceptualized as a group of customers or potential purchasers who represent sufficient profit or public relations potential as to be attractive to the marketer, and who as a group can be identified and reached with a tailored marketing mix (Fluid Communications: 2004). It can be defined as the total demand for goods; the

set of all actual and potential buyers of goods or services; the place where people buy and sell; the process by which buyers and sellers of goods, services and factors of production interact to determine prices and quantities (Financial Dictionary & Glossary: 2001).

According to the above conceptualisation, the product market under study is the market for trainer's skills and geographically, it is the Bangladesh Market. It is a mechanism or a process through which trainers and buyers interact with each other in order to make transactions.

Marketing

Another useful concept that deserves attention is marketing. Identifying the product and defining the market is only the stepping-stone. The product needs to be sold fulfilling customer satisfaction. Here comes the concept of Marketing, which can be defined as the commercial processes involved in promoting and selling and distributing a product or service (WordNet 2.0: 2003). "In general, marketing activities are all those associated with identifying the particular wants and needs of a target market of customers, and then going about satisfying those customers better than the competitors. This involves doing market research on customers, analyzing their needs, and then making strategic decisions about product design, pricing, promotion and distribution" (MOTI: 2001).

Theoretical Approaches

This is possible to analyse the problem at hand under various approaches, such as Welfare Economics Approach, Public Choice Approach, Policy Sub-system Approach, Marketing Approach, etc. Welfare Economics Approach aims at maximizing social welfare or aggregate of individual welfare through government intervention in the market in order to correct 'market failures' (Arrow, 1963; Quade, 1976; Gilroy and Wade, 1992). On the other hand, Public Choice Approach (Niskanen, 1971; Buchanan, 1978) based on Economics views an individual as a rational being who is motivated to maximize self-interest. The aggregate of self-interest equals national interest. Government intervention in the market only distorts the market mechanism and hinders individual's self-interests. Thus, government intervention is unwarranted and market forces should be allowed to operate freely. Yet Policy Sub-system Approach (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993; Mawhinney, 1993) conceptualises any policy arena

comprising various sub-systems, which in turn are comprised of various advocacy coalitions. Various actors, such as politicians, public servants, interest groups, NGOs, academics, think tanks, journalists, etc. may form a Policy Sub-system. An advocacy coalition may comprise actors from both public and private sectors belonging to a common belief system who strive to achieve their common goals. Policy intervention emerges out of the fusion of various advocacy coalitions, relatively stable parameters and external events. Still it is possible to conceptualise the issue at hand as a marketing problem and various marketing strategies and policy intervention may be prescribed under the Marketing Approach.

The training and development market in Bangladesh has a strong Welfare Economics bias. It is characterized by government intervention in order to maximize social welfare. On the other hand, the rational choice logic of action underpins the title of this paper. However, the emergence of advocacy coalitions in the training and development sub-system is also witnessed at the present time. Whatever theoretical underpinning is acknowledged, marketing strategies are needed to expand the boundaries of the training and development profession. Consequently, this paper will take a multi-disciplinary approach and draw on all relevant approaches.

CURRENT MARKET SITUATION

The training and development market in Bangladesh is a highly regulated one. It is compartmentalized into two groups: Public Sector Market and Private Sector Market. The Private Sector Market can again be divided into two groups: Corporate Sub-sector and NGO Sub-sector. Inter-sector/sub-sector mobility is very limited. Penetration of one sector/sub-sector by another is a reality. It is also noteworthy that any market study should examine at the first instance the demand and supply for a product or service. Against this backdrop, the market situation in Bangladesh can be analysed from two viewpoints: Demand-side Analysis and Supply-side Analysis.

Supply-side Analysis

The Public Sector Market is characterized by in-house training facilities. Consequently, every cadre of the Bangladesh Civil Service has its own training providers. Likewise, major government departments and autonomous bodies including State Owned Enterprises have their own training providers. Defence forces also have their own Management level training providers, such

as Defence Services Command and Staff College, National Defence College, etc. These public sector providers mostly cater to the needs of their own departments and/or ministries. Some providers, such as Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre (BPATC) cater to the needs of various government service cadres. Bangladesh Academy for Rural Development (BARD), Comilla, Rural Development Academy (RDA), Bogra and National Institute of Local Government (NILG), Dhaka cater to the management needs of rural development and local government functionaries and elected representatives. An important characteristic of the public sector providers is the provision of in-service training. These providers mostly conduct in-service training programs, although some providers, such as Bangladesh Institute of Management (BIM) offer pre-service training programs as well. The Public Sector Market on the supply side has reached the saturation point. Against a backdrop of the demand for a downsized government and limited funding, there is little or no scope of further expansion in this sector.

Within the Private Sector Market, big NGOs, such as BRAC, PROSHIKA, Association for Social Advancement (ASA), etc. have their own in-house training facilities for their executives. These training facilities can be utilized by other NGOs as well. Most medium sized NGOs have their own training facilities. However, this service is available for field-level workers and clientele groups. They do not conduct management level training programs for their executives. At the time of initial recruitment, executives are provided with a short orientation program, which is informal in nature. Later, they undergo informal on-the-job training. It appears that, on the supply side there is a scope of expansion in this sub-sector.

Limited training service providers characterize the Corporate Sub-sector of the Private Sector Market. Rapport Bangladesh Limited may be identified as the leading provider of corporate training services. However, various industry associations, such as BGMEA and business interest groups, such as DCCI, FBCCI, etc. also provide training services. These providers are limited in number and there is a scope of expansion in this sub-sector.

Besides NGOs and Corporate Training Providers, there are other training providers in the Private Sector Market. Universities are major players in this sub-category. Especially, private universities, such as North-South University,

BRAC University, IUBAT, etc. are significant emerging forces. Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BUET) is a pioneer in this sub-category. It offers management level training programs for both in-service and pre-service clientele groups. For example, presently it is offering a course on Apparel Production Management and another course on Environmental Management. There is scope for further expansion in this sub-sector.

Demand-side Analysis

On the Demand-side, the Public Sector Market is characterized by in-service training and it has almost reached the saturation point. In most cases, demand roughly equals supply. Few Sub-sectors have potentials for further expansion. These Sub-sectors include Education, Health, Disaster Risk Reduction and Taxation. Training entrepreneurs can arrange for a detailed market study in order to capture the market share. Prospective training programs should be highly specialized.

The NGO Sub-sector of the Private Sector Market has a significant potential for demand-side expansion. There is a prospect for expansion of both in-service and pre-service training demand. However, private sector providers are in a better position to tap this market. Again, detailed market study can be arranged to identify specific market needs.

The Corporate Sub-sector is almost untapped. As discussed before, there are a limited number of management level training providers in this Sub-sector, which has been experiencing a rapid growth since the 1990s. Most corporations hire business graduates and put them on probation for two years. During this period, they are required to undergo on-the-job training. If non-business graduates are hired, they are encouraged to get a business degree on a part-time basis. If BBAs are hired, they are encouraged to do an MBA. It appears that there is a dearth of both pre-service and programmed in-service training programs in this Sub-sector. Consequently, most corporations look for experienced people while recruiting. Not surprisingly, fresh graduates find it extremely difficult to get a break. Training entrepreneurs can come forward to fill up this gap of pre-service training. However, such training programs must have a strong industry-linkage. Provision of in-service training at all levels (beginners, mid-level management, and top management) has a significant potential if training programs are carefully designed to cater to the needs of the

time. Such training programs must focus on on-the-job reality, rather than on academic plane. Both public and private sector training providers can vie for a slice of this market. Training entrepreneurs can move forward to explore this untapped market.

OPPORTUNITIES

From the above analysis, it is clear that a window of opportunity exists for marketing of trainer's skills. Both individual trainers and training organizations may avail of these opportunities. This section will highlight these opportunities.

Business Development

Business development is the first and foremost opportunity. The private sector, particularly the corporate sector, is almost untapped and it is fast growing. So there is a great business opportunity for new providers in the private sector. Training entrepreneurs can seize this opportunity and start up new business. Existing providers, particularly in the public sector, can seize this opportunity as well. They can expand their business. For example, National Academy for Educational Management (NAEM) has recently won a contract amounting to Tk. 27 Lakh (app.) to provide computer training to the staff of IDEAL project under the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education. Providers have to look for similar opportunities. In this way, the public sector training providers can transform themselves from not-for-profit organizations to profit-making organizations.

Employment Opportunity

Establishment of new business and expansion of existing providers will definitely generate new employment opportunities. New generation trainers will surely energize the training and development sector. This will strengthen the profession.

Career Prospect

Business development will increase the career prospect of all trainers. Presently, trainers have a very limited career prospect. Expansion will necessitate positions with higher responsibilities and new recruits, and thereby increasing promotion prospects. This will also increase inter-sector and intra-sector mobility.

Increased Income

Business development will increase income of trainers. Full time trainers will be able to work on a part-time or casual basis in addition to their own work. Thus, they will be able to increase their income. Trainers' income can also be increased in the form of honorariums and bonuses. Growth in the industry may lead to higher salary offer for the trainers particularly in the private sector.

Recognition

Presently, trainers are looked down upon by other professions. Training organizations, particularly in the public sector, are considered as dumping stations for unfit and unwanted bureaucrats. With higher income and increased employment opportunity and career progression, trainers will be able to get recognition from peers, organization heads, government and the society.

CHALLENGES

There are obstacles to overcome in order to avail of the opportunities offered by the market. Some of the obstacles can be removed easily, but some of them are deeply rooted and may take a longer time to overcome. However, any concerted and motivated attempt surely will be successful. Major challenges are discussed below :

Attitudinal Change

Trainers have a know-it-all attitude. This attitude may be blamed for inappropriate and ineffective training programs. Training programs and training curricula are often designed not on the basis of proper training needs assessment, but are based on what trainers think it should be. This is not an impediment for trainers working in a highly regulated environment. However, this is particularly problematic for marketing of trainer's skills. If trainers wish to sell their skills in the market, they must be ready to respond to the calls from the market forces. This requires a change in the know-it-all attitude on the part of the trainers.

Market Study

This article is the first attempt to discuss the problems and prospects of

marketing of trainer's skills in Bangladesh. What this article suggests is just an indication. Sector-specific and detailed market analysis is needed for a successful marketing of trainer's skills. Now the question is who will do this. Trainers themselves have to take the responsibility. Many training institutes in the public sector have a planning/research and development wing. The activities of this wing are often limited to evaluation of programs and assessment of trainee performances. They can be encouraged to undertake original market analysis in the area of their expertise. Training entrepreneurs can play a lead role in this regard.

Customer Orientation

In order to successfully market their skills, trainers need customer orientation. Trainers often perceive themselves as teachers or Gurus. However, market forces will treat them as service providers only. Consequently, it is an imperative on the part of the trainers to consider the buyers of their skills as customers. These buyers may include individuals or organizations or both. Customer satisfaction should be the motto of the trainers and trainers should adopt a customer-oriented outlook. This outlook will promote 'customer first' environment in an organization and also in the psyche of trainers.

Competitiveness

Marketing of trainer's skills will involve competition. Trainers may have to compete with each other. Public sector providers may have to compete with private sector providers. Market forces will reward the most competitive providers only. As a result, trainers must be ready to increase their competitiveness.

Outsourcing

For widening the market and increasing opportunities for more providers, outsourcing of training providers needs to be encouraged. Thus, companies and NGOs may be persuaded to outsource their training providers, rather than relying on in-house on-the-job training. Public sector organizations may also be encouraged to outsource some of their training providers retaining the core training programs for the in-house providers. However, preference for excellence should be the basis of outsourcing.

Deregulation and Privatisation

The mercerisation process in the long run may call for deregulation and privatisation initiatives in the Public Sector Market. Corporatisation of public sector providers may come up on the agenda. Particularly, deregulation will be needed for outsourcing in the public sector. Trainers will have to prepare themselves to face this challenge in the long run.

Self-regulation

Marketing of trainer's skills will necessitate self-regulation on the part of the training and development industry. This will be particularly needed to eliminate any unscrupulous providers and also to guard against any unethical practices on the part of the trainers. Such a framework is also needed for dispute resolution as well as enhancing and maintaining the professional standard. Bangladesh Society for Training and Development (BSTD) is particularly suited for this job.

STRATEGIES

Both opportunities and challenges concerning marketing of trainer's skills have been outlined above. In order to utilize the opportunities by overcoming the challenges, trainers need to develop sound strategies. The following is an indicative list of strategies, which may be pursued by the trainers' community. First, trainers should unite themselves and pursue the issue in a concerted way. Presently, BSTD is the only effective trainer's association. Unfortunately, its membership size is not very healthy. In order to achieve something tangible, trainers should rally behind organizations like BSTD. Second, Self-development is another priority area, which needs urgent attention. It is commonly felt that many trainers are reluctant to update their knowledge and skills. Trainers should strive to enhance their professional standard. Third, trainers should pay particular attention to public relation matters. The onus is on the trainers to preach the value of training, and their abilities to perform the job efficiently and in a cost effective manner. This will need a concerted PR campaign. Fourth, training entrepreneurs should urgently undertake market studies to explore scope and extent of market opportunities, and to devise ways to penetrate the market.

CONCLUSION

Trainers have special skills. This article indicates that there is a potential market demand for these skills. Although both demand and supply at the Public Sector Market have reached a saturation point, the Private Sector Market, particularly the Corporate Sub-sector is fast growing, and the growth prospect of training and development in this area is significant. Amongst pre-service and in-service training, the former has a larger potential. New training organizations may flourish in the Private Sector Market. Existing actors in the Public Sector Market may also look for opportunities in the Private Sector Market. Thus, marketing of trainer's skills offers opportunities, but not without challenges. Trainers' community, particularly training entrepreneurs need to come forward and seize the opportunities by overcoming the challenges.

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